

SEMANTIC ANALYSIS OF OIL IN FOOD LEXEMES IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

Mamataliyeva Navbakhor Khujamberdiyeva

Teacher of Termez State University

Khayitmurodova Mokhira Abdikhofiz kizi

Student of Termez State University

mohiraxayitmurodova@gmail.com

Annotation: This study provides an in-depth semantic analysis of food lexemes related to oil in English and Uzbek languages, exploring their linguistic nuances, cultural significance, and metaphorical uses. The comparison highlights how each language categorizes and values different types of oils, reflecting diverse culinary traditions and dietary practices.

Key words: oil, lexemes, food, Uzbek, English, metaphorical use, classification, types of oil.

INTRODUCTION

Due to the peculiarities of the people's natural habitat, their main historical occupation, their cultural and historical development, food and the national cuisine associated with it is one of the most specific areas of the people's culture, which, of course, is reflected in its linguistic support (on the naming

system, in particular). The sphere of human life associated with food is diverse and complex, as is its conceptual reflection in the human mind¹.

MAIN PART

Analyzing food lexemes related to oil in both English and Uzbek languages provides fascinating insights into cultural practices, dietary habits, and linguistic nuances. Oils, which are integral to cooking and food preparation, vary greatly in terms of types, uses, and cultural significance between the two languages. **Lexical Categories and Classification English: Types of Oil:** Olive oil, vegetable oil, canola oil, sunflower oil, peanut oil, coconut oil, etc. **Culinary Uses:** Frying, baking, sautéing, dressing. **Descriptors:** Cold-pressed, extra virgin, refined, unrefined. **Uzbek: Types of Oil:** Zaytun yog'i (olive oil), o'simlik yog'i (vegetable oil), kungaboqar yog'i (sunflower oil), yong'oq yog'i (peanut oil). **Culinary Uses:** Qovurish (frying), pishirish (baking), qo'shish (adding to dishes). **Olive Oil:** Symbol of Mediterranean cuisine, associated with health benefits. **Vegetable Oil:** Common in Western cooking for its neutral flavor and versatility. **Peanut Oil:** Popular in American and Asian cuisine for frying due to its high smoke point. **Uzbek: Zaytun Yog'i:** Olive oil is less common but increasingly popular due to perceived health benefits. **Kungaboqar Yog'i:** Sunflower oil is widely used in everyday cooking. **Paxta Yog'i:** Cottonseed oil, traditionally used in Uzbek cuisine, especially for frying. **Oil:** Can connote richness, health (in terms of healthy fats), and luxury (e.g., truffle oil). **Grease:** Often used negatively to indicate excess fat or unhealthiness. **Yog' (Oil):** Generally connotes nourishment and essential cooking ingredient. **Yog'li (Greasy/Fatty):** Can imply richness of flavor but

¹ Soars, L. In search of English food / L. & J. Soars // Headway. Oxford University Press, 1997. - P. 22.

also potential health concerns if used excessively. **Metaphors and Idioms.** **English: “Oil the wheels”:** To make a process run smoothly. **“Oil and water”:** Refers to things that do not mix well together². **“Sutning yog’i”:** Literally "the milk of the oil," used to describe something extremely good or precious. **“Yog'da suzish”:** Literally "swimming in oil," used to describe being in a state of abundance. **Olive Oil:** Borrowed from Old French and Latin. **Canola Oil:** Derived from "Canadian oil, low acid." **Uzbek: Zaytun Yog'i (Olive Oil):** Derived from Arabic influence. **Paxta Yog'i (Cottonseed Oil):** "Paxta" is borrowed from Persian. **Oil:** Historically referred to any liquid fat; now more specifically denotes plant-based oils or mineral oils. **Yog':** Originally referred to all kinds of fat; modern usage is more specific to liquid oils, with solid fats often termed “yog’li.” **Synonyms and Hyponyms: Synonyms for “Oil”:** Fat, grease (in certain contexts). **Hyponyms of “Oil”:** Olive oil, coconut oil, fish oil, etc. **Synonyms for “Yog”:** Moy (another term for oil, more literary). **Hyponyms of “Yog”:** Zaytun yog'i (olive oil), paxta yog'i (cottonseed oil). **“Oiled”:** Can mean lubricated or made smoother. **“Oily”:** Often has a negative connotation when referring to greasy food or substances. **“Yog’langan”:** Means lubricated, can be used metaphorically for being well-prepared. **“Yog’li”:** Refers to fatty or greasy, both literally and metaphorically. **Taboos and Euphemisms: Grease:** Often used euphemistically to avoid directly mentioning unhealthiness. **Yog’li:** Used carefully as excessive fat is often discouraged in modern dietary advice, despite being traditional. **Oil:** Represents a universal concept of liquid fat, essential in cooking. **Yog':** Similarly represents a fundamental concept of fat, crucial in traditional cooking.

CONCLUSION

² English Learners Digest / A variety of American Foods. 2002. ~№ 4. -P. 11

The lexemes reflect the dietary importance and cultural practices associated with oils. English emphasizes diversity in types and uses of oil, reflecting a broad culinary spectrum. Uzbek, while also recognizing various types, shows a strong traditional preference for certain oils like cottonseed oil, which is less common in the West. English lexemes often highlight health aspects (e.g., extra virgin olive oil), whereas Uzbek terms may more frequently emphasize traditional and practical uses. Both languages use oil-related metaphors to convey smoothness or abundance, reflecting oil's essential role in both cultures.

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